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Article

De Santis O, Audran R, Pothin E, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of a chimpanzee adenovirus-vecto
Haller MJ, Atkinson MA, Wasserfall CH, et al. Mobilization without immune depletion fails to restore ir
Fischer K, Bahlo J, Fink AM, et al. Long-term remissions after FCR chemoimmunotherapy in previousl
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Rapaport MH, Nierenberg AA, Schettler PJ, et al. Inflammation as a predictive biomarker for response
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Raatz SK, Johnson LK, Picklo MJ. Consumption of Honey, Sucrose, and High-Fructose Corn Syrup Pro
Genovese MC, Hsia E, Belkowski SM, et al. Results from a Phase IIA Parallel Group Study of JNJ-4034
Ma JK, Drossard J, Lewis D, et al. Regulatory approval and a first-in-human phase I clinical trial of a
Mily A, Rekha RS, Kamal SM, et al. Significant Effects of Oral Phenylbutyrate and Vitamin D3 Adjunct
Bhatia A, Sharma RK, Tewari S, Narula SC. A randomized clinical trial of salivary substitute as an adj
Andres C, Plana M, Guardo AC, et al. HIV-1 Reservoir Dynamics after Vaccination and Antiretroviral T
Debrah AY, Specht S, Klarmann-Schulz U, et al. Doxycycline Leads to Sterility and Enhanced Killing o
Hunter DJ, Beavers DP, Eckstein F, et al. The Intensive Diet and Exercise for Arthritis (IDEA) trial: 18
Nilsson C, Hejdeman B, Godoy-Ramirez K, et al. HIV-DNA Given with or without Intradermal Electrop
Lo MM, Mbao V, Sierra P, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of Onderstepoort Biological Products' Rift
Fuchs CS, Azevedo S, Okusaka T, et al. A phase 3 randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial
Joachim A, Nilsson C, Aboud S, et al. Potent functional antibody responses elicited by HIV-I DNA prin
Wheatley CM, Baker SE, Morgan MA, et al. Effects of exercise intensity compared to albuterol in indiv
Treven P, Mrak V, Bogovič Matijašić B, Horvat S, Rogelj I. Administration of probiotics Lactobacillus r

	LLM: Claude Sonnet 4				
DOI	1a	1b	2a	2b	3a
https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(15)00486-7	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1111/cei.12731	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially
https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2015-06-651125	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djv302	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2015.22	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1186/s13028-015-0171-6	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.3945/jn.115.218016	No	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially
https://doi.org/10.3899/jrheum.141580	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.12416	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially
https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0138340	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.2334/josnusd.57.241	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01062-15	No	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/civ363	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2015.03.034	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0131748	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.4102/ojvr.v82i1.857	No	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdv027	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0118486	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmed.2014.12.002	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-8519	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

3b	4a	4b	5	6a	6b	7a	7b	8a
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Partially	Yes
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Partially
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Partially	No	Partially
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Partially
Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
No	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Partially	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No

8b	9	10	11a	11b	12a	12b	13a	13b
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Partially	No	No	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially
No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
No	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	Partially	Partially	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	No	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	No
No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

14a	14b	15	16	17a	17b	18	19	20
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Partially	No	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Partially	Yes	Yes
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Partially
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Partially
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
No	No	No	Partially	Partially	No	Yes	No	Partially
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes

				sem	1.28	1.22	0.55	-	3%
				std	5.72	5.44	2.45	-	15%
				avg	23.65	10.60	2.70	-	68%
21	22	23	24	25	YES	NO	PARTIALLY	Count	CLAUDE
Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	31	4	2	37	86.50%
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	16	13	8	37	54.10%
Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	24	12	1	37	66.20%
Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	24	12	1	37	66.20%
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	22	10	5	37	66.20%
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	20	16	1	37	55.40%
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	21	8	8	37	67.60%
Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	32	3	2	37	89.20%
Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	18	14	5	37	55.40%
Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	30	4	3	37	85.10%
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	24	9	4	37	70.30%
Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	20	15	2	37	56.80%
Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	30	7	0	37	81.10%
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	21	16	0	37	56.80%
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	32	3	2	37	89.20%
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	18	16	3	37	52.70%
Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	34	1	2	37	94.60%
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	19	13	5	37	58.10%
Yes	No	No	No		19	17	0	36	51.40%
Yes	Yes	No	No	No	18	19	0	37	48.60%

2%	3%	2%	5%	10%	0%	4%
9%	15%	17%	22%	44%	0%	30%
81%	55%	68%	5%	25%	0%	10%
CHATGPT	GEMINI	COMBINED	>90%	>90%	>90%	COMBINED
94.60%	75.70%	-	0	1	0	-
75.70%	44.40%	-	0	0	0	-
78.40%	58.30%	-	0	0	0	-
75.70%	54.10%	-	0	0	0	-
75.70%	51.40%	-	0	0	0	-
59.50%	35.10%	-	0	0	0	-
83.80%	35.10%	-	0	0	0	-
81.10%	51.40%	-	0	0	0	-
77.00%	51.40%	-	0	0	0	-
75.70%	51.40%	-	0	0	0	-
78.40%	40.50%	-	0	0	0	-
81.10%	39.20%	-	0	0	0	-
83.80%	83.80%	-	0	0	0	-
86.50%	54.10%	-	0	0	0	-
90.50%	78.40%	-	0	1	0	-
73.00%	64.90%	-	0	0	0	-
94.60%	78.40%	-	1	1	0	-
93.20%	58.10%	-	0	1	0	-
90.50%	56.80%	-	0	1	0	-
70.30%	39.20%	-	0	0	0	-